

COPPER CORROSION IN ACIDS

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Paper Received On: 20 July 2024

Peer Reviewed On: 24 August 2024

Published On: 01 September 2024

Abstract

Acid concentration increases corrosion rate reaches a maximum another decreases. This is due to the fact that at very high concentration of acids ionization is reduced. Because of this many of the common acids such as acetic acid, sulfuric, hydrofluoric as other are virtually inert in the pure state or 100% concentration at moderate temperature of grains. Other differences in the metal can be chemical, metallurgical or mechanical in nature. Examples are impurities such as oxides and other inclusions, grain size, orientation, dislocation arrays, differences in composition of the microstructure, precipitated phases, localized stresses, scratches and nicks. Highly polished surfaces are used in only special cases. Very pure materials are more corrosion resistant than commercial materials.

Keywords: *Corrosion, Alloy, Acid concentration, Grains.*

Introduction: Copper is different from most other metals in that it combines corrosion resistance with high electrical and heat conductivity, formability, machinability and strength. When alloyed except at high temperatures, copper exhibits good resistance to urban, marine and industrial atmospheres and water. Copper is a noble metal and hydrogen evolution is not usually a part of the corrosion process. For this reason, it is not corroded by acids unless oxygen or other oxidizing agents are present (nitric acid). For example, the reaction between copper and sulfuric acid is not thermodynamically possible, but corrosion proceeds in the presence of oxygen and the products are copper sulfate and water. Reduction of oxygen to form hydroxide ions is the predominant cathodic reaction in copper, its alloys, and copper-base alloys. Copper-base alloys are resistant to neutral and slightly alkaline solutions. With the exception of those containing excess ammonia which cause stress corrosion and sometimes rapid general attack.

In strongly reducing conditions at high temperatures (300-400°C) copper alloys.' are often superior to stainless steels and gain less alloys. The most common copper base alloys are brass (Cu4-7.n). bronze cupronickel (Cu_Ni) Copper and brasses are subjected to erosion corrosion or impingement attack. The bronzes and Aluminium brass are much better in this respect. The bronzes are stronger and harder. The cupro-nickel with small iron additions are also superior in erosion corrosion resistance. Copper and copper alloy's are available in duplex tubing (inside one metal, outside another) in combination with steels, aluminum and stainless steels.

EXPERIMENTAL BACK GROUND:

With this background the Corrosion study on copper metal has been carried out under different media viz acids, bases. Neutral organic solvents etc. and the study has en correlated to the available literature. Rectangular Copper plates are used throughout the experiment solutions of different concentrations viz 0.1. 0.5.1N.4N have been prepared and standardized. The copper plates are clipped in the (effective solutions for 1 to 5 hours and the corrosion study is measured in the form of weight loss basis. The results are given in the 'Tables. The potentials have been measured using Copper electrode as the Reference electrode.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS:

Weight loss of Copper (mg)

S No	MEDIUM	0.1N	0.5N	1N	4N
1	HCl	12	12.5	11	12.25
2	H ₂ SO ₄	07.5	10.24	14.5	34.00
3	HNO ₃	08	17	12	74.50

Weight Loss(mg)	1 Hour	2 Hour	3 Hour	4 Hour	5 Hour
0.1N HCl	0.90	2.5	6	8	14
0.5N HCl	0.92	2	2.5	7	13
1N HCl	0.90	2	3.5	8	11.5
4N HCl	1.8	3.5	5	8.5	11

Weight Loss(mg)	1 Hour	2 Hour	3 Hour	4 Hour	5 Hour
0.1N H ₂ SO ₄	1	2	4	5	6
0.5N H ₂ SO ₄	1.5	3	5	7	9
1N H ₂ SO ₄	2	4	6	9	12
4N H ₂ SO ₄	3	8	12	24	36

Weight Loss(mg)	1 Hour	2 Hour	3 Hour	4 Hour	5 Hour
0.1N HNO ₃	2	3	4	5	6
0.5N HNO ₃	2	3	6	12	15
1N HNO ₃	1	2	3	4	6
4N HNO ₃	1.5	3	4.5	6.5	7.5

From the above results the lot low i nu conclusions have been drawn .The corrosion of copper in acidic medium is considerably lower than that of iron. This is due to the noble act um of Copper on the electrochemical series, but in mine medium sodium hydroxide, potassium hydroxide the rate or corrosion is more than Iron. The potential measured copper against calomel electrode are also less than that of Sunder different media. This is also in support of the noble behavior of the metal. Corrosion of copper on 4N HN O₃ is quite higher. The order of rate of corrosion are as follows HNO₃>H₂S0₄> H Cl corrosion in alkali is also quite high.

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